

live larvae/tiller, compared with 0-1 (mean 0.4) live larva/ tiller in check plots.

The increased carryover of larvae with zero-tillage wheat could be a

factor limiting the next year's rice crop, if nurseries are planted before 20 May. Zero-tillage wheat is safe to grow because *Scirpophaga* do not feed on wheat. *Sesamia inferens* (Wlk.) and

S. uniformis (Dudgn.) have been reported to attack rice and wheat in small numbers, but they could not be detected during this study. □

Rice-based cropping systems under irrigation in North India

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Rice is becoming a more important crop during the Jun-Oct monsoon season in irrigated areas of North India because of its higher yield potential and better market price. It has even replaced maize in areas where soils are coarse textured with high permeability. We evaluated rice-based cropping systems for those areas.

A 1983-86 field trial included 9 crops fitted into 7 crop rotations: four 1-yr and three 2-yr. Soil was well-drained (saturated hydraulic conductivity 1 cm/h) sandy loam

Rice-equivalent yields and net returns from rice-based cropping systems evaluated in North India, 1983-86.

Rotation	Rice-equivalent grain yield (t/ha per yr)	Net return (\$/ha per yr)	Benefit-cost ratio
Rice - wheat ^a	9.9	500.00	1.22
Rice - linseed - black gram ^a	8.3	423.00	0.98
Rice - toria - wheat - black gram ^a	12.3	491.30	0.77
Rice - linseed - maize (fodder) ^a	10.8	532.50	1.28
Rice - sugarcane + wheat - potato - green gram ^b	13.1	413.90	0.53
Rice - toria - sugarcane - wheat - black gram ^b	10.2	416.70	0.80
Rice - wheat - sugarcane - potato - black gram ^b	15.4	524.20	0.59
CD (5%)	1.0	50.90	—

^aOne-year crop rotation. ^bTwo-year crop rotation.

(Fluvent) with neutral soil reaction and medium soil fertility.

A 2-yr rotation of rice - wheat - sugarcane - potato - black gram gave the highest rice-equivalent grain yield; rice - linseed - black gram gave the lowest (see table). Rice - wheat, the most popular crop rotation of the area, was next to last in grain production. The best 1-yr crop

rotation was rice - toria - wheat - black gram.

Rice - linseed - maize (fodder) gave the highest net returns, equal to rice - wheat, rice - toria - wheat - black gram, and rice - wheat - sugarcane - potato - black gram. The highest benefit-cost ratio was with rice - linseed - maize (fodder), followed by that with rice - wheat. □

ERRATA

D.K. Kundu, F.N. Ponnampereuma, and H.U. Neue. An improved method of representative sampling from aerobic soil solutions. 11 (6) (Dec 1986), 35-36.

The corrected article is reprinted below.

An improved method of sampling representative solutions from aerobic soils

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Analysis of a solution collected in situ from aerobic soil can be used for characterizing the soil chemical

environment of upland rice. However, it is difficult to obtain samples from aerobic soils with moisture contents near field capacity (FC). The displacement method for well-packed FC moist soil columns has not been tested for validity under normal pot culture conditions. We evaluated samples collected by the conventional displacement method from three FC moist potted soils with different hydraulic conductivities.

Twelve kilograms each of air-dried (>2 mm sized) Luisiana clay, Maahas clay, and Pila loam soils were placed in 16-liter porcelain pots fitted at the bottom with drainage (coarse sintered glass) tubes. The soils were brought to FC moisture using tensiometers.

To collect soil solutions, 0.5% KSCN as displacing liquid was poured on the soil surfaces. The displaced solutions were drained into measuring cylinders. We tested the collected solutions for SCN-ion at regular intervals. Drops of acidic FeCl₃ solution were used as the indicator (a blood red-colored complex is formed).

From the fast-draining Luisiana clay and Pila loam soils, we could collect only 20-30 ml of soil solution. Beyond this volume, the leachate was diluted by the displacing liquid. In slow-draining Maahas clay, no displacement appeared in the first 200 ml. About 175 ml of soil solution is needed for a complete analysis; the displacement method was not appropriate for soils